

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

FOREIGN POLICY OF THE COMMUNIST PARTY OF VIET NAM IN THE PERIOD 1945 – 1946. HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE AND LESSONS LEARNED IN THE DEFENSE OF SOVEREIGNTY IN THE EAST SEA

Nguyen Tran Tan Hiep

Student, Institute of Social Sciences and Humanities, University of Tyumen, Russia, ORCID: 0000-0003-1313-4879

Nguyen Quynh Trang

Student, Faculty of History, Hanoi National University of Education, Vietnam
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Abstract

Between 1945 and 1946, when the young Democratic Republic of Vietnam faced many enemies, the CPV and President Ho Chi Minh demonstrated the skill of diplomacy to bring Vietnam out of its predicament, preparing for a long war of resistance. The author describes the domestic and international situation between 1945 and 1946, the diplomatic activities of the DRV government and the foreign policy views of the CPV. It is shown how «avoiding simultaneous confrontation with many enemies», President Ho Chi Minh has cleverly used the conflict of interests of imperialist powers to defend the conquests of revolution and independence of the country. The author recalls a number of valuable lessons that can be drawn from the history of Vietnamese diplomacy in studying foreign policy during the difficult period 1945-1946.

Keywords: Vietnamese diplomacy, period 1945 – 1946, East sea, multilateral, independence

Introduction

Foreign affairs are the most important issue in international political relations, the basis for the development of economic, political, cultural ... fields of each country. Foreign affairs can help a country prosper, expand economic and political relations with other countries in the world, thereby developing the domestic economy and society if there is a Reasonable foreign policy, but it is also external activity that can cause a country to become poor, lagging, and destabilizing if it does not have the right foreign policy. Foreign policy of any country also aims at three basic goals, that is to contribute to the protection of national independence, sovereignty and territorial integrity; to take advantage of the most favorable international conditions for national development and raise its position and influence on the international arena. Our country's foreign policy is also not an exception.

In the process of leading the revolution, our Party has always shown its bravery and wisdom in making foreign policies and policies consistent with each historical period. Especially in the period (1945-1946), when the country was in extremely difficult situation, "a thousand pounds hung hair", with clever, flexible and creative foreign policies, our Party practiced Middle spirit and force to solve each difficulty, bring the country out of enemy siege. For the above reasons, the author chose the topic "*Foreign policy of the Communist party of Viet Nam in the period 1945-1946. Historical significance and lessons learned in the defense of sovereignty in the East Sea*" made an essay to clarify the correctness of the Party's foreign policy, contributing to the victory of the war against reality the French people invaded, firmly defended the national independence. At the same time, it also shows the values that foreign policy of that period brought in the struggle to protect Vietnam's sovereignty in the East Sea.

Content

1. International and domestic context in the period 1945 - 1946

1.1 International context in the period 1945 - 1946

On 5/1945, World War II ended in Europe with victory belonged to the Allies. The world situation is changing at an extremely rapid pace. Big countries adjust their foreign policies. On the Allies side, relations between the countries gradually shifted from cooperation in the war to confrontation in peace. The world order changed, changing from the unipolar order established after World War I to the bipolar order that is still called the Ianta bipolar order, led by the US and the Soviet Union. These two superpowers, conducting arms races, contend for their influence in regions of the world.

Also at this time, the other major Allied countries also tried to consolidate the colonial system. Britain and France are the two great powers that won the war, but in a weakened position, the politics were not stable, so it was necessary to quickly restore the economy, stabilize politics and maintain the role of great power after the war. In order to do so, Britain and France had to protect their colonial system and their sphere of influence.

Meanwhile in Asia and Africa, the movement to fight against the war of aggression and Western colonial domination became extremely strong. The struggles in different countries took place in many different forms but all had the same tendency to overthrow the yoke of external domination, liberate the country from the Western imperialism and colonialism. Movement to fight for national liberation in these countries gradually spread to Europe and spread around the world.

Thus, we can see that the international context in the years 1945 - 1946 had many complicated

developments, deeply and deeply impacted on many international relations and had a direct impact on the situation in Vietnam.

1.2 Context of Vietnam in the period 1945 - 1946

At the height of the world war, in 1942, President Ho Chi Minh pointed out the opportunity and predicted the time when our country's revolution would be successful "1945 - Vietnam is independent"¹. He called upon the nation's compatriots: "The invading faction is almost at the end of its destruction. The Allies were about to compete for ultimate victory. The opportunity for our nation to liberate is only in a year or a half. Time is very fast, we have to do it fast!"² By August 1945, under the direct leadership of the Indochinese Communist Party led by leader Ho Chi Minh - the revolution broke out and won. The birth of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam opens a new era for the entire Vietnamese people.

In the early days of the country's establishment, the people's government faced many great challenges. Socio-economic life is in turmoil and collapse after the war. The chronic food scarcity during wartime had its consequences in the years 1945, when more than two million people died of starvation; all production, economic, financial, and commercial activities stagnated. The banking system of Indochina is still in the hands of French capitalists. Meanwhile, the Chiang Kai-shek army allowed to circulate the devalued Chinese currency, arbitrarily set the exchange rate for the ROC currency and the Indochinese currency, to manipulate the market in the North; The dumb policy of the French colonialists makes 95% of our people illiterate.

Another challenge that our country faces - that is, at the same time, we have to deal with many rival military forces of major countries present in our country. In the north, nearly 200,000 ROC troops entered Vietnam in the name of disarming Japanese troops from the 16th parallel onwards, bringing groups of Vietnamese in exile in China. South Vietnam at this time also had about 2.6 thousand British - Indian troops to disarm the Japanese army.

In October 1945, Britain signed an agreement formally recognizing French civil rights in Indochina. On January 1, 1946, Britain signed an agreement empowering France to disarm Japanese troops south of the 16th parallel. In return, the Frenchman ceded some interests in Syria and Lebanon. In addition, during the Japanese occupation of Indochina, France had about 50,000 soldiers including prisoners being held by Japan and recruits scattered in the vicinity of Indochina. After the war, 15,000 French soldiers held by the Japanese in South Vietnam during the March 9 coup were released and armed again. The new French expeditionary army was rushed to the South Vietnam. On September 23, 1945, the French opened the second invasion of Vietnam. In addition, there were about 60,000 Japanese troops in Vietnam waiting to disarm at this time.

Thus, four major military powers are occupying our country (Japan, Britain, France and the ROC forces) and three out of the five major countries are permanent members of the UN Security Council engaged in disarmament for Indochina with the sole goal of seeking to erase the revolutionary government and restore the order of Western colonialism here.

At that time, President Ho Chi Minh cum Minister of Foreign Affairs and the Party Central Standing Committee soon saw the possibility of using diplomacy as a sharp weapon to actively participate in the process of self-defense of the revolutionary achievements, divide, isolate the enemy. From the beginning, Vietnamese diplomacy has actively promoted the offensive position against the enemy's intrigue and traps, and carried out great tasks that seemed impossible to perform.

2. Vietnam's foreign policy in the period 1945 - 1946

2.1 Foreign policy goals

In the face of very complicated domestic and international situations, our state soon issued the foreign policy of the government of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam. One month after declaring Vietnam's independence, on October 3, 1945, our country's foreign policy was published in the form of a state document: "Communication on the foreign policy of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam", published in the newspaper "Save the Nation", October 3, 1945.

The objective of the policy is: to protect the results of the August Revolution, but first of all to maintain and strengthen the people's government that has just been established throughout the country. Next, bring Vietnam to complete and permanent independence; "Vietnam is still in the period of fierce struggle, all foreign policy must have the primary purpose of helping the struggle to win by all gentle or resolute methods"³. At the same time, our foreign policy also clearly states that we will work with the Allied countries to rebuild world peace.

2.2 Foreign policy choices

The "Communication on the foreign policy of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam" (October 3, 1945) set forth a very specific and correct foreign policy, suitable for each audience.

With the Allies, Vietnam wishes to maintain friendship and sincere cooperation on the basis of equality and mutual assistance, to build lasting world peace.

With France, our policy is to protect the lives and property of French expatriates in accordance with international law, as long as they live peacefully and respect the law, sovereignty and independence of Vietnam. We wish to build friendly relations on the basis of respect for the equal rights and autonomy of France. As for the French colonialists plotting against and invading our country, we resolutely fight.

With neighboring countries, especially the people of Khmer and Laos, Vietnam bases its relations on the

¹ Ho Chi Minh: full set (2000), Publisher: National Politics, Chap 3, page 230

² Ho Chi Minh: full set (2000), Publisher: National Politics, Chap 3, page 505 - 506

³ Nguyen Phuc Luan (2001), Vietnam's diplomacy for the cause of independence and freedom (1945 - 1975), National Political Publishing House, pp. 39

principle of self-determination of the nation. Having been under French domination, the people of the three countries must join forces to remove that yoke, help each other gain independence and maintain their independence. Moreover, the three countries have close economic relations, will help each other in the construction work, and move forward together on the path of progress.

*“With sub-ethnic groups around the world, the Government of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam is ready to be friendly and closely cooperate on the principle of equality to support each other in the cause of building and maintaining independence”.*⁴

In the context of complicated developments in the world and in the country. At the same time, we also have to deal with relationships with many other forces. Therefore, we need to have flexible policies, setting priority tasks. Our main enemy right now is the invading French colonialists. We need to concentrate our forces against the main enemy, and neutralize the other opposing forces so that we can free our hands to fight the French. Our Party's theme: *“We must separate the invading French colonialists to fight, don't put the French, British, and Indians (Indian soldiers in the British army) into one attack and don't consider them as equal enemies each other, don't attack France, only attack the French colonialists.”*⁵

On this basis, the Standing Committee of the Party Central Committee, the Government and President Ho Chi Minh have come to the strategic decision “Peace to advance”. The revolutionary command at that time correctly generalized the various possibilities to maintain the revolutionary achievements without necessarily following a monolithic path. I do not host the chapter “fight to the end” because this chapter will make me isolated and drain my strength. We use “peace to advance” measures, take advantage of contradictions in the enemy's ranks, skillfully and flexibly turn the hand-in-hand agreements (British-France and China-France) related to our country's interests form a tripartite agreement with our participation, and at the same time create a peace with one side to take advantage of time to strengthen internal forces and strengthen strength to deal with other enemies.

Thus, our diplomacy in this period is multilateral, flexible, when making concessions, when resolute and always affirming the country's independence and self-reliance.

2.3 Deploy foreign policy

** Foreign Policy with the Army of the Republic of China*

The government of the Republic of China has long had its own plans for Indochina. As soon as the French army fell, and the Japanese army entered and occupied North Indochina in September 1940, the government of the Republic of China began to prepare for the plan of “Chinese troops entering Vietnam” and Chapter “Destroy Communism, Capture Ho Chi Minh”. Chiang Kai-shek has prepared a force of Vietnamese henchmen so that when he sends troops into Vietnam, he will establish a pro-Chiang Kai-shek government and the

goal is to overthrow the Communist Party and destroy the Viet Minh.

However, our revolutionary government upholds the slogan “friendly China-Vietnam” and implements mediation with soft and calm tactics. The purpose of these policies was to take advantage of Chiang Kai-shek's forces present in Vietnam as a counterweight to the forces of the French colonialists, curbing the policy of the Paris government to soon restore control in the Indochina; have time to stabilize the situation in the country and have free time to deal with France.

In the public statements of the Government of Vietnam on Vietnam-China relations, as well as the letters and telegrams from President Ho Chi Minh to Chiang Kai-shek, we always affirm our friendship and long-standing ties year between the two countries. President Ho Chi Minh also often visited the generals of the Republic of China in Vietnam, on the one hand to establish close diplomatic relations, on the other hand, to get to know the generals, taking advantage of the greedy side material words to limit resistance; understand their internal conflicts and those with external ones. From there, take advantage of the contradictions to do useful things for us.

With many changes in the domestic situation, the Communist Party of Vietnam withdrew into secret activities in the form of self-disbanding on October 11, 1945. In order to limit destructive activities of political groups pro- ROC, President Ho Chi Minh represented the Viet Minh to carry out many joint meetings with representatives of the Vietnam Nationalist Party and the Vietnamese Revolutionary Alliance to unify the common principles and sign the agreements that forced the Vietnamese Nationalists and the Vietnamese Revolutionary Allied Society to agree on the principles of solidarity, cooperation, for the national interest, support the resistance war in the South, supported the government's policies... We reserved the positions of vice president, foreign minister, and economic minister for the Vietnamese Revolutionary Allies, the Vietnamese Nationalist Party and 70 seats in parliament without a general election. This ingenious and correct strategy has appeased the opposition of ROC generals and pro-ROC groups, and contributed to thwarting their plots of sabotage and subversion. Although we make concessions, we still have clear operating principles, always affirming the path of independence and self-reliance.

At the same time, the Communist Party of Vietnam also demonstrated the great political force of the people supporting the revolution to support diplomatic activities. Typically, the parade of 30,000 people in Hanoi capital. The parade was nominally to applaud the Allied mission, but in fact it was to show the people's forces supporting the revolutionary government and President Ho.

Thus, Vietnam's diplomacy with the Republic of China in this period used three main measures: Demonstrating force, Taking advantage of contradictions to avoid conflict; Compromise has principles. Thanks to the measures and policies of the

⁴ Ministry of Foreign Affairs: Main documents of the Geneva Conference (1995), Hanoi, pp. 25-26

⁵ Vu Doan Ket (2007), Vietnam's foreign policy, World Publishing House, page 24

Vietnamese government to pacify and restrain the opposing forces of Chiang Kai-shek's army, the North of our country had a relatively stable period to carry out the policy of resistance war and national construction building and strengthening the people's administration; delaying the French expeditionary army to the North and creating conditions to support the resistance in the southern compatriots.

** Foreign policy with the French colonialists*

After World War II ended, France once again plotted to invade Vietnam. They sent troops to occupy South Vietnam first, then intend to expand the war to the North. However, before the fierce resistance from the armed forces in South Vietnam, the French colonialists expressed concern. Especially at this time, the French colonialists also had to confront the ROC forces in the North. Since then, France decided to sign the Sino-French Treaty in Chongqing on February 28, 1946, returning a number of French concessions and conceding to the Republic of China a number of economic rights in Indochina. In return, the Republic of China accepted the French to the North to disarm the Japanese army.

The Sino-French treaty is a disadvantage for us. Before, we took advantage of the contradiction between the French and Chiang to avoid confrontation with these two great forces, but now they are working together to compromise. This situation forced us to come up with new, flexible and appropriate foreign policies to deal with Chiang Kai-shek and the French.

Our policy gradually turned to concessions and détente with France, but still maintaining political independence. The goal of détente with France was to push the ROC troops home, turning the two-way agreement into a three-way agreement. Finally, on March 6, 1946, the Preliminary Agreement between Vietnam and France was signed in Indochina. The Agreement includes the following basic contents: France recognizes Vietnam as a free country, having its own government, parliament, army and finances, and a member of the Indochinese federation, within the Union of Nations France. Regarding the reunification of the three regions, the French government is committed to recognizing the decisions of the people directly judged through the referendum. In return, the Vietnamese government agreed to let 15,000 French troops enter North Vietnam to replace the Chinese army in the task of disarming the Japanese army and bringing them home. The French troops mentioned above will be withdrawn within 5 years.

The signing of the Preliminary Agreement was a wise diplomatic measure, taking advantage of the French-ROC conflict, especially when they were compromised. The preliminary agreement reflected our use of the strategy of dividing the enemy, using the replacement clause of the Sino-French Agreement to create an opportunity to push the Republic of China troops out of the country, avoiding the risk of having to deal with the enemy with two hostile forces at the same time. At the same time, the Agreement also creates a

peaceful period so that our government and people can build and strengthen their forces and prepare for a long-term resistance war.

The preliminary agreement on March 6, 1946 was the first international legal document that the Democratic Republic of Vietnam signed with a foreign country. The agreements on March 6 expanded the Vietnam-France contact and negotiation framework, creating a legal basis for the diplomatic struggle in Vietnam.

At the request of the French side, on March 24, 1946, President Ho Chi Minh met Georges Thierry d'Argenlieu in the Gulf of Tonkin. At the meeting, the two sides agreed on the next steps for the Vietnam-France negotiations to resolve the remaining issues of the Preliminary Agreement. The two sides agreed to convene a preparatory meeting for Da Lat as suggested by the French, but we required the participation of government delegates from France; agreed to convene early formal negotiations between the two sides in Paris immediately after the conclusion of the preparatory meeting; The French side invited the Vietnamese National Assembly delegation and President Ho Chi Minh to visit France in May 1946.

The official Vietnam-France negotiations at Fontainebleau took place from July 6, 1946 to August 1, 1946, we had goodwill, but the reactionary French colonialists always plotted to completely disrupt the negotiations officially, went to nullify the Preliminary Agreement on March 6, 1946. They almost carried out their plot. On September 13, 1946, our negotiating team left for the country. However, President Ho Chi Minh decided to stay a few more days to continue discussing with the French government in order to save the tense situation of France-Vietnam relations, prolonging the much needed peace in Indochina. President Ho Chi Minh has 8 times with Moutet to attend political, diplomatic, cultural - social events and 8 times to Moutet private house to discuss. Representative of the French Government Sainteny recounted: "*Ho Chi Minh did not return with the Vietnamese delegation. He made it clear that he wanted to go to the end. Like Marius Moutet, he wanted to avoid a breakup and signed with Moutet the Temporary Covenant to save the situation. Still, he fears the worst. He foresaw the possibility of an outbreak of armed conflict and told me firmly: If it is necessary to fight, we will fight. One of you can kill ten of us. Ten of us will kill one of you. But in the end, it is you who will be discouraged and give up*"⁶ Results 1 am on September 15, 1946 A provisional agreement of 11 articles was signed between Ho Chi Minh and Minister Moutet representing the French government.

This Agreement temporarily recognized the commitments of Vietnam and France on the basis of the Preliminary Agreement, in order to resolve pressing issues in the relationship between the two countries, affirming the need to immediately stop all conflicts. The French side will ensure the exercise of freedom and democracy in the South, release the Vietnamese arrested by the French, and the Vietnamese side will

⁶ Do Hoang Linh, Ho Chi Minh with the negotiation process of the Fontaine Conference (URL: <http://www.lyluanchinhtri.vn/home/index.php/nhan-vat-su->

[kien/item/1676-ho-chi-minh-voi-qua-trinh-dam-phan-hoi-nghi-phongtennoble.html](http://www.lyluanchinhtri.vn/home/index.php/nhan-vat-su-kien/item/1676-ho-chi-minh-voi-qua-trinh-dam-phan-hoi-nghi-phongtennoble.html))

concede to France a number of economic and cultural rights in Vietnam. The reactionary French colonialists also demanded that President Ho Chi Minh agree to withdraw the armed forces in the South to the North, but he resolutely refused.

Thus, by conceding more to France a number of economic and cultural rights and maintaining an independent stance within the French Union, we will achieve a continued ceasefire, commitment to freedom and democracy for the people Southern people. Therefore, giving us more time to prepare our military and economic forces... to deal with the enemy.

The preliminary agreement on March 6, 1946 and the interim treaty of September 14, 1946 demonstrated the multilateral, flexible foreign policy of the Party and President Ho Chi Minh. Thanks to these policies, we can not only eliminate fewer enemies, but also have more time to prepare for the national resistance war.

** Foreign policy with other countries*

As confirmed in the Communiqué 3/10/1945, with major countries and countries in the Allies against fascism, Vietnam is very friendly and sincerely cooperates on the stance of equality and mutual love. The United States is a big country in the Allies against fascism. The attitude of the US government will affect the French establishment of a colony in Indochina, the expansion of Chiang's army. From September 1945 to February 1946, President Ho Chi Minh sent eight messages, letters, telegrams and notes to the US President and Secretary of State, introducing new developments in the situation of Vietnam; denouncing France's re-invasion of Vietnam and violations of the principles stated in the Atlantic Charter and the United Nations Charter; proposed that the United States recognize Vietnam's independence.

The Vietnamese government also regularly maintains relations with US representatives present in Vietnam, such as the US Mission in Indochina, the office of the Strategic Intelligence Agency. Our purpose is to enlist the Americans present in Hanoi to assist in the containment of General Chiang and the French forces. President Ho Chi Minh also had meetings with US diplomats. In September 1946, while in France, the President visited the US Embassy in Paris, met the US Ambassador and then received the US Ambassador's staff to greet him. The transactions of the leaders of Vietnam had a certain impact on the attitude of the United States in the Indochina issue. The Pentagon document commented on the matter: "*While no action was taken to meet the demands raised by Ho Chi Minh, the US was also not willing to help the French*"⁷ Thus, our foreign policy at this time is people-to-people diplomacy, proactively establishing friendly Vietnamese-American associations in order to take advantage of US neutrality, creating conditions for peace, and restraining the forces of Chiang and France in the region Vietnam.

For a country considered a "communist stronghold", since the founding of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, President Ho Chi Minh has sent many telegrams and letters to the government and

Soviet people. Typical among them is the telegram sent on September 22, 1945, right after Vietnam declared its independence. Although at that time, the Soviet Union did not respond, but it also showed the Party's diplomatic policy of multilateralization and diversification with all countries in the world.

With respect to other countries, we advocate friendly, cooperative and equal relations, enlisting help and support from outside. For the French and Vietnamese people, there is no enmity, always showing a friendly attitude, expressing the desire to cooperate. We are only against the reactionary French colonialists who intend to invade our country.

3. Historical significance

Vietnam's foreign policy in the period 1945 - 1946 was very flexible and clever. The bold mark of the diplomatic victory of this period was the counter-measures and ingenious acts at the same time with many major countries, dealing with four foreign armies with over 300,000 soldiers present in Vietnam. Relations between major countries always have many conflicts and conflicts of interest, but when necessary, they are ready to compromise and trade with each other despite the interests of the Vietnamese people, and seek to impose on Vietnam and Indochina. But we skillfully took advantage of conflicts between countries and had a strategy suitable for each object: keeping the US neutral, patiently avoiding all conflicts of Chiang, resolutely resisting the French invaders in the region South, and at the same time find a peaceful solution when Chiang and France compromise to allow French troops to the North.

Thus, the reality has proved that, that period 1945-1946 will forever go into the heroic history of the nation as unforgettable years. The young Vietnamese diplomacy led by President Ho Chi Minh, the Party and government of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam have made excellent contributions to defending our sovereignty and nascent independence while our forces are still weak, and at the same time creating favorable conditions to take advantage of time to build up forces, take advantage of the most favorable international conditions for the development of the country; enhance its position and expand its influence in the international arena. In short, Vietnam's foreign policy in this period is a flexible, multilateral diplomacy based on the principle of "dĩ bất biến, ứng vạn biến", making principled concessions and taking advantage of conflicts in international relations enemies.

These foreign policies, formed from the early days of Vietnam's establishment, laid the foundation for revolutionary and modern Vietnamese diplomacy. These policies throughout the development of Vietnam's diplomacy as well as the development of the country and have left many achievements.

4. Applying lessons learned in current diplomacy

Currently, Vietnam is an independent and self-reliant country that is increasingly rising in the context of the world's many changes. Since the end of the war, Vietnam has been trying to build the country, move

⁷ Pentagon documents, volume 1, pp. 17-18

towards socialism, and contribute to world peace and security. Vietnam's achievements have been reflected in the numbers on economic growth or the positions that Vietnam has been taking in international groups. In addition to the achievements that Vietnam has achieved, it is impossible not to mention the instability in the East Sea in which Vietnam is a country with a dispute. With the above, Vietnam's diplomacy is currently facing enormous challenges that the context brings. Vietnam's diplomacy needs to be clever to bring into full play the country's potential, combine national strength and the strength of the times, and at the same time be a sharp weapon to fight to protect the country's sovereignty and territorial integrity Vietnam

Facing the challenges that Vietnam's diplomacy is currently facing, the lessons learned from a difficult time from 1945 to 1946 still promote their values:

Firstly, it is the principle of "*dĩ bất biến, ứng vạn biến*" that President Ho Chi Minh and our Party have used very successfully in the period 1945 - 1946. The principle of independence, self-reliance, unity and Territorial integrity are inalienable principles. That is something that not only for Vietnamese diplomacy, but also for all Vietnamese people with Vietnamese blood, must protect at any cost. Historically, millions of Vietnamese have fallen to protect what is most sacred to them, which is independence, self-reliance, unity and territorial integrity. However, in the current context, in order to successfully defend the above principles, Vietnamese diplomacy needs to be really skillful and flexible in dealing with the parties, in order to maximize national strength, increase Vietnam's position in the international arena, protecting the country from afar.

Second, it is a lesson about diversification and multilateralization in diplomacy. In the period of 1945 - 1946 when the country had just gained independence, the government was still very young and had not been recognized by any country, then President Ho Chi Minh, the Central Committee of the Party and the Government determined a path. multilateral and diversified diplomacy with all countries in the world. Today, the domestic and international contexts have changed a lot, but the lesson of diversification is still very important. The proof is in its foreign policy that Vietnam has identified itself as a friend of all countries in the world. Vietnam does not accept to participate in any military alliance, does not allow foreign countries to set up military bases on Vietnamese territory, and does not use force or threaten to use force against other countries. That also makes Vietnam a peaceful, stable and cooperative country with all other countries around the world. There is rarely a place like Vietnam where the ambassadors of India and Pakistan can talk happily, the ambassadors of Israel and Palestine can drink tea together and especially the historic meeting between US President Donald Trump and North Korean leader Kim Jong Un in Hanoi. That has shown the correctness of Vietnam's multilateral foreign policy.

Ultimately, it is a lesson in enlisting international support. The period 1945 - 1946, when the country faced many difficulties. The Party Central Committee and President Ho Chi Minh made the most of the

international support to achieve the goal of maintaining the nascent peace. The evidence is the times when President Ho Chi Minh sent letters to senior leaders of great powers such as the US, the Soviet Union, the Republic of China or the United Nations when Vietnam was just born and had not been recognized by anyone take. In the complex context of the current world situation, Vietnam needs to make the most of this lesson to enlist international support to promote the values of the nation and the times, defend the country, fight struggle to preserve the nation's territory and territorial sea. The evidence is that Vietnam has maximally enlisted international support in disputes with China in the East Sea and as a result, Vietnam has maintained its sovereignty over islands and archipelagos in the region South China Sea, without further complicating the dispute.

Conclusion

Currently, the common trend that countries around the world are aiming for is peace, cooperation and development. Countries have more and more economic, political and social relationships. In order for these relationships to become good and sustainable, a country needs to have good diplomatic relations with other countries in the world. region and around the world. Vietnam, after 30 years of renovation, has a great advantage that the political and social situation is basically stable, but we are also facing many great challenges. The Party and State of Vietnam continue to implement the foreign policy of independence, self-reliance, openness, diversification and multilateralization of international relations, and proactive international integration with the motto that Vietnam is ready to be a friend. and is a reliable partner and responsible member of the world community striving for peace, independence and development. Our foreign policy and guidelines began with the formation of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam state. Until now, those policies are still sharp tools to help Vietnam protect its independence, sovereignty, territorial integrity, and develop in terms of economy, culture and society. Learning about Vietnam's foreign policy helps us better understand the country's diplomatic activities. From there, we can draw valuable experiences to apply and create to contribute to the development of the country. At the same time, the knowledge that we gain through studying foreign policies and diplomatic activities also helps us in our conduct and daily work. The period 1945 - 1946 was the time when the new Democratic Republic of Vietnam was formed. At this time, the domestic and international situation is very complicated. Vietnam's diplomacy at this time must promote its full potential to maintain independence and sovereignty and move the country forward. This was the period when Vietnam's diplomacy was clearly shown with specific goals and tasks. The victory of foreign policy in the period 1945-1946 proved the correct line of the Party, raised the art level in the diplomatic strategy of President Ho Chi Minh and our Party, leaving valuable experiences in current foreign relations.

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